

“AN ANALYSIS OF CSR POLICY OF PRIVATE SECTOR BANKS INCLUDED IN NIFTY”

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Abstract:

The spirit of giving had moved from charity to philanthropy in order to sustain business and maintain the social as well as environmental capacity. Corporate Social Responsibility has gained growing appreciation and recognition as a new and up-coming form of corporate governance in business. It is correct to say that Indian Companies have performed extremely well in the discharging their responsibilities towards Corporate Social Responsibility and bringing extraordinarily changes in the country by enhancing social well-being of the people and in uplifting the weaker sections of the society. The companies were required to formulate a CSR policy as an integral part of the overall business policy so as to provide a road map for CSR activities. The present study highlights the various activities which should be included in the CSR policies and analyse the CSR spending of five private banks in the year 2020-21. Government guidelines on practices of corporate social responsibility broadly cover all categories such as education, rural development, environment, healthcare, sustainable development, women empowerment, sports, infrastructure, etc. The scope of study is related to five private sector banks which are included in NIFTY as on November 2021. The resultant banks were HDFC Bank, Indusind Bank, Kotak Mahindra Bank, ICICI Bank and Axis Bank. With the introduction of Corporate Social Responsibility in 2013, now in 8 years there have been significant changes in the Corporate Social Responsibility policy brought by the Ministry of Corporate Affairs.

Keywords: CSR, CSR policy, CSR activities, Average profit, private sector banks

1. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the corporate are working with twin objectives, firstly to earn profits and secondly for the benefit of society. The objective of serving the society is known as ‘Corporate Social Responsibility’. The concept of CSR is not new to the business world. This concept dates back to ancient period. According to our holy Vedas, man can live individually but can survive only collectively. Public

welfare was regarded as the main aim of the State. During the end of 1800's and beginning of 1900s, the creation of welfare schemes took a paternalistic approach which aimed at protecting the employees as well as retaining them along with improving the quality of work life.(Carroll 2008; Heald 1970). Now the corporations are not treated as merely economic entities operating to earn profit. In the judgement of Supreme Court in National Workers Union vs. P. R. Ramakrishnan and others [1983 SCR (1)9], the changing face of a modern day corporations along with all its newly given attributes was traced. It tries to establish company as an entity accountable to all its stakeholders along with society at large.

The companies were required to formulate a CSR policy as an integral part of the overall business policy so as to provide a road map for CSR activities. Accordingly, the CSR policy was expected to include the following points:

- Care for Stakeholders: The companies should respect and take care of all the stakeholders i.e. suppliers, customers, employees, shareholders and society at large, etc.
- Ethical Functioning: Companies should not engage in unfair, corrupt or abusive practices. Ethics, accountability and transparency should be taken care of.
- Respect for Human Rights: Companies should respect human rights for all.
- Respect for Employees – their rights and welfare: Companies should ensure that the workplace environment is safe, humane and hygienic. The companies should provide all opportunities to its employees for enhancing their skills for career advancement.
- Respect for Environment: Companies should take steps to prevent pollution by recycling, managing and reducing waste. It should also manage natural resources in a sustainable manner and ensure optimal use of natural resources.
- Inclusive and social development: Companies should undertake activities in their areas of operations for the development of communities economically and socially. Companies should work for the upliftment of disadvantaged and underprivileged sections of the society.

• **EVOLUTION OF CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY**

The evolution of CSR in India may have started in 1965-66. The table below shows the various dates on which government took steps towards the evolution of CSR:

Table 1

S. No.	Dates	Activities
1	1965-66	Formal engagement of the Indian corporate sector may have initiated with the seminars related to CSR.
2	December 2009	First set of guidelines introduced by the MCA.
3.	April 01, 2010	Release of the Department of Public Enterprises (DPE) guidelines
4.	July 08, 2011	Release of National Voluntary Guidelines by the MCA
5.	2013	The process of responsible Corporate Governance through CSR was finally enshrined into law with the enactment of Companies Act, 2013 by Indian Parliament

6.	2013	In Lok Sabha Bill was passed on December 18, 2012 In Rajya Sabha Bill was passed on August 08, 2013. The Act was notified in the Gazette of India on August 30, 2013.
7.	2014	Rules notified on Feb 27, 2014, Effective from April 01, 2014.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Vethirajan. C, Ramu. C (2019) in his article on “Customers Perception of CSR Impact on FMCG Companies – An Analysis” shows that CSR is actually about making sure that the company can produce on a sustainable base to ensure the equality to all its stakeholders, since CSR has come a long way in India.

Smith’s definition of CSR (2001) gave hints of the need of making CSR part of a company’s strategic perspective in order to be able to fulfill its long term obligations towards society. This was reaffirmed by Lantos (2001) that same year, who pointed out that during the twenty-first century society would demand corporations to make social issues part of their strategies

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The present study aims to achieve the following objectives:

- a) To highlight the various activities which should be included in the CSR policies.
- b) To highlight the CSR policy of five private sector banks included in NIFTY
- c) To highlight the composition of CSR committee of five private banks
- d) To analyse the CSR spending of five private banks in the year 2020-21.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

- a) Research Type : Exploratory
- b) Sampling Unit : Private Sector Banks included in NSE- NIFTY
- c) Sample size : Five
- d) Data Type : Secondary Data
- e) Data Source : Annual Reports of respective private sector banks
- f) Time Period : 2020-21
- g) Scope of the study : The scope of study is related to 5 private sector banks which are included in NIFTY as on November 2021. The resultant banks were HDFC Bank, Indusind Bank, Kotak Mahindra Bank, ICICI Bank and Axis Bank. The paper also takes the references of various articles written by various experts on CSR.

5. APPLICABILITY OF CSR PROVISIONS

According to section 135 of the Companies Act, 2013, every company fulfilling any one of the following conditions during any financial year shall constitute a Corporate Social Responsibility Committee of its Board called:

- a) Net worth of Rs. 500 crore or more

- b) Turnover of Rs. 1000 crore or more
- c) Net profit of Rs. 5 crore or more

Section 135 is applicable to all companies, whether public company or private company including companies registered under section 8 as well as foreign companies having its branch/project office in India.

Such a company needs to spend at least 2 percent of their average net profit in the previous three years on CSR activities. If Company fails to spend such amount, disclosures are to be made for the same.

The CSR committee should consist of 3 or more directors including at least 1 independent director.

- **ACTIVITIES WHICH MAY BE INCLUDED BY COMPANIES IN THEIR CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY POLICIES**

CSR Policy relates to the activities to be undertaken by the company as specified in Schedule VII of the Companies Act, 2013 and the expenditure thereon. The Rules provide that the CSR Policy of a company shall, include the following:

1. A list of CSR projects or programmes which a company plans to undertake activities as mentioned in Schedule VII, specifying modalities of execution of such project or programmes and implementation schedule of the same; and
2. Monitoring process of such projects or programmes

As per Schedule VII of Companies Act, 2013, activities which may be included by companies in their Corporate Social Responsibility Policies are mentioned herein below:-

Table 2

S. No.	CSR Activities	
1	Eradicating hunger, poverty and malnutrition	Promoting health care
		Preventive health care and sanitation
		Contribution to the Central Government's Swach Bharat Kosh set-up for the promotion of sanitation and making available safe drinking water
2	Promoting education	Special education
		Employment enhancing vocation skills especially among children, women, elderly and the differently abled
		Livelihood enhancement projects
3	Promoting gender equality	Women Empowerment
		Setting up homes and hostels for women and orphans
		Setting up old age homes, day care centres and other facilities for senior citizens as required
		Activities undertaken in order to reduce inequalities faced by economically and socially backward groups
4	Ensuring environmental sustainability	Protection of flora and fauna
		Conservation of natural resources

		Agro-forestry, Animal welfare Maintaining quality of water, air and soil Ecological balance Contribution to the Clean Ganga Fund set-up by the Central Government for rejuvenation of river Ganga
5	Protection of national heritage including art and culture	Renovation of buildings and sites of historical importance and works of art Establishing public libraries Development and promotion of traditional art and handicrafts
6	Measures taken for the benefit of armed forces veterans, war widows and their dependents	Central Armed Police Forces (CAPF) and Central Para Military Forces (CPMF) veterans and their dependents and widows
7	Training to promote rural sports	Recognized sports at national level Paralympics sports Olympic sports
8	Contribution to the Prime Minister's National Relief Fund	PM CARES Fund Central Government's fund for socio economic development Central Government's fund for relief and welfare of the SCs, STs, OBCs, minorities and women
9	Contribution to incubators or R&D projects in the field of science and technology, medicine and engineering, funded by the Central or State Government or PSUs or any agency of the Central or State Government	Contributions to public funded Universities Contributions to IITs Contributions to National Laboratories and autonomous bodies established under Department of Atomic Energy Contributions to Department of Biotechnology Contributions to Department of Science and Technology Contributions to Department of Pharmaceuticals Contributions to Ministry of Ayurveda, Yoga and Naturopathy, Unani, Siddha and Homoeopathy Contributions to Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology and other bodies, namely DRDO, ICAR, ICMR and CSIR
10	Rural development projects	
11	Slum area development	Area as declared by Central or State Government or any competent authority

12	Disaster management	Relief, rehabilitation as well as reconstruction activities
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The company should give preference to local area for CSR activities.

6. ANALYSIS OF CSR ACTIVITIES CARRIED BY PRIVATE SECTOR BANKS

For the purpose of the study all 5 private banks have been taken which are included in NIFTY as on November 2021. The resultant banks were HDFC Bank, Indusind Bank, Kotak Mahindra Bank, ICICI Bank and Axis Bank. The analysis of CSR activities carried by these banks keeping in view the statutory requirements as per section 135 of the New Companies Act, 2013 is mentioned herein below:

(1) Brief outline of different Bank's CSR Policy:

Table 3

S. No.	Name of the Bank	CSR Policy
1	AXIS Bank Ltd.	<p>The CSR philosophy of AXIS Bank Ltd. is to make significant and measurable contributions in the lives of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • socially, • economically, • financially and physically excluded, • disadvantaged and challenged communities <p>of India with an integrated approach of development that concentrates on creating opportunities for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • enhancing opportunities for livelihood, • improving quality of education at all levels and skills development, • creating awareness among public on health, hygiene and financial literacy, • making available formal banking channels for un-banked sections of the society, • promoting environmental sustainability, and • supporting health and sanitation initiatives <p>which may be carried out by the Bank directly or through Axis Bank Foundation or implementing partners.</p>
2	HDFC Bank Ltd.	<p>CSR of HDFC Bank Ltd. is implemented under the aegis of 'Parivartan' - the umbrella brand for all the social initiatives of the Bank. It aims to transform the communities in which the Bank operates through multiple initiatives in the areas of</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education, • Skill training, • livelihood enhancement,

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health Care, • Environmental Sustainability and • Rural Development. <p>The social activities of the bank are guided by CSR Policy which is duly approved by the Board and driven by the vision of “Creating Sustainable Communities”.</p>
3	ICICI Bank Ltd.	<p>CSR has been a long-standing commitment at ICICI Bank Ltd. which forms an integral part of Bank’s activities. The contribution of the bank towards social sector development includes various revolutionary interventions, and is implemented through the involvement of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • stakeholders within the Bank, • the Group and • the broader community. <p>In order to expand the ICICI Group’s CSR activities, the Bank established the ICICI Foundation for Inclusive Growth in 2008. In last few years ICICI Foundation has developed major projects in specific areas, and has worked towards direct project implementation rather extending financial support to other organizations. The objective of ICICI Bank is to promote meaningful socio-economic development in the country and enable participation of a larger number of people in India’s economic progress. ICICI Bank aims to highlight the vital areas of development that need investments and intervention, and which can enable the realization of country’s potential for growth and prosperity. The CSR Policy outlines the:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • governance structure, .operating framework, • monitoring mechanism and • guiding principles for choosing the CSR projects/ activities to be undertaken. <p>The ICICI Bank’s CSR activities are largely focused in the areas of: education,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • health, • skill development, • sustainable livelihoods, • environment, • rural development and • other activities like disaster relief or other activities under Schedule VII of the Companies Act, 2013.
4	Indusind Bank Ltd.	<p>‘Good Ecology is Good Economics’ is the mission of Indusind Bank Ltd. which guide the CSR Policy of the bank. It intends in creating value for all stakeholders and emerge as a ‘Best-in-Class’ bank that is dedicated to</p>

		<p>sustainable and balanced economic growth. The Bank believes that the business of the Bank grows consistently and responsibly, benefitting those it directly serve while also promoting the:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • well-being of the employees, • natural environment and • the community at large. <p>IndusInd Bank designs and supports sustainable CSR programs that primarily empower and benefit:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • marginalized and weaker sections of society, • high risk and high-stressed communities.
5	Kotak Mahindra Bank Ltd.	<p>Kotak Mahindra Bank Ltd. recognizes the fact that it has a huge opportunity to bring about a positive change in the lives of the communities through its business activities and CSR initiatives. The bank seeks to be a trusted partner and contributes considerably towards the</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • economic, • environmental and • social growth of the nation and • is also committed to contribute towards United Nation’s Sustainable Development Goals. <p>This policy sets the Bank’s mission, vision, governance and CSR focus areas to fulfill its inclusive growth agenda in the country. The bank endeavors to align its CSR projects and programmes with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Indian Government initiated social development programmes and • Interventions and United Nation’s Sustainable Development Goals.

(2) Composition of the CSR Committee:

The CSR committee of any company should fulfil the following roles namely;

- To formulate and recommend the CSR policy to the board of directors;
- To recommend the activities which are to be undertaken by the company;
- To recommend the amount of expenditure to be incurred on each activity;
- To monitor the implementation of CSR policy.

The committee should consist of three or more directors of which at least one director shall be an independent director.

The role of Board of Directors is very important in this regard. The role includes:

- Form a CSR Committee;
- Approve the CSR Policy;
- Disclose the CSR policy in the report of Board of Directors;
- Upload the CSR policy on the company’s website;
- Ensure Implementation of CSR activities;

- Ensure at least 2% of the net profit should be spent on CSR activities;
- If allocated amount is not spent fully, disclose reasons for the same.

The table below shows the names of the directors and the nature of directorship of five private sector banks:

Table 4

S. No.	Name of the Bank	Name of the Directors	Designation / Nature of Directorship
1	AXIS Bank Ltd.	Shri Rakesh Makhija	Chairman – Independent Director
		Shri Rajesh Dahiya	Executive Director (Corporate Centre)
		Shri T. C. Suseel Kumar (w. e. f. 14. 12. 2020)	Non-Executive (Nominee) Director
		Shri Rajiv Anand	Executive Director (Wholesale Banking)
2	HDFC Bank Ltd.	Mr. Umesh Chandra Sarangi	Independent Director & Chairperson
		Mr. Sanjiv Sachar	Independent Director
		Mr. Malay Patel	Independent Director
		Mrs. Renu Karnad (w. e. f. June 03, 2020)	Non- Executive Director
		Mr. Aditya Puri	Former Managing Director
		Mr. Kaizad Bharucha (w. e. f. November 25, 2020)	Executive Director
		Mr. Aditya Puri ceased to be a member of the Committee pursuant to the cessation of his tenure as Managing director	
3	ICICI Bank Ltd.	Mr. Radhakrishnan Nair	Chairman - Independent Director
		Ms. Rama Bijapurkar	Independent Director
		Mr. Uday Chitale	Independent Director
		Mr. Anup Bagchi	Executive Director
4	Indusind Bank Ltd	Mrs. Akila Krishnakumar	Chairperson of the CSR Committee
		Mr. Rajiv Agarwal	Member
		Mr. Sanjay Asher	Member
		Mr. Sumant Kathpalia	Managing Director & CEO
5	Kotak Mahindra Bank Ltd.	Mr. Prakash Apte	Chairman/ Independent Director
		Mr. C. Jayaram	Member / Non-Executive Director
		Mr. Dipak Gupta	Member / Joint Managing Director
		Prof. S. Mahendra Dev	Chairman (till March 14, 2021) / Independent Director

Nearly all the private sector banks have four members in their CSR committee including independent directors, managing director.

(3) Number of meetings of CSR Committee held during the year

Table 5

Particulars	AXIS Bank Ltd.	HDFC Bank Ltd.	ICICI Bank Ltd.	Indusind Bank Ltd.	Kotak Mahindra Bank Ltd.
Number of meetings of CSR Committee held during the Year	4	3	3	2	1

As per the above table, Kotak Mahindra Bank Ltd. hold least number of CSR committee meetings i.e. only one meeting while AXIS Bank Ltd. hold maximum number of CSR committee meetings i.e. 4 meetings among all five private sector banks. HDFC Bank and ICICI Bank hold three CSR committee meetings, while Indusind Bank holds two meetings in a year.

(4) CSR amount spent / unspent for the financial year

The table below highlights the average profit of five private sector banks and the amount spent and unspent on CSR activities during the financial year 2020-21:

Table 6

Particulars	AXIS Bank Ltd.	HDFC Bank Ltd.	ICICI Bank Ltd.	Indusind Bank Ltd.	Kotak Mahindra Bank Ltd.
Average net profit	4,532.70 Crore	31,393 Crore	92.26 Billion	601130 Lakhs	7,113.74 Crore
Two percent of average net profit	90.65 Crore	627.86 Crore	1,845.3 Million	12023 Lakhs	142.27 Crore
Surplus arising out of the CSR projects or programmes or activities of the previous financial years	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Total amount spent for the Financial Year	90.93 Crore	634.91 Crore	2,005 Million	9,472.42 Lakhs	79.40 Crore
Amount available for set off in succeeding financial years	0.28 Crore	7.05 Crore	159.7 Million	--	--
Total Amount transferred to	---	---	---	2,600.00 Lakhs	63.59 Crore

Unspent CSR Account as per Section 135(6) of the Act					
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All the private sector banks have allocated 2 percent of their net profit for the purpose of CSR activities. AXIS Bank Ltd., HDFC Bank Ltd. and ICICI Bank Ltd. have spent more than 2 percent of their net profit. However, Indusind Bank Ltd. and Kotak Mahindra Bank Ltd. have spent less than 2 percent of their net profit in CSR activities and thus transfer the unspent amount to Unspent account as per section 135 (6) of the Companies Act.

(5) Items under which banks have undertaken their CSR activities

The table below highlights the various CSR activities which have been undertaken by the private sector banks:

Table 7

S. No.	Name of the Bank	Type of Projects	Item from the list of activities in Schedule VII of the Companies Act, 2013
1	AXIS Bank Ltd	Ongoing Projects	Livelihood enhancement, vocational skills training, conservation of natural resources and rural development
			Promoting Education & Skill Development
			Education, Reducing inequalities faced by socially and economically backward groups, rural development
		Other than Ongoing Projects	Promotion of health care including preventive health care and sanitation and disaster management
2	HDFC Bank Ltd.	Ongoing Projects	Promoting Education
			Vocational Training and Livelihood Enhancement
			Sanitation
			Rural Development Projects
		Other than Ongoing Projects	Promoting Education / Gender Equality
			Vocational Training and Livelihood Enhancement
			Ensuring Environment Sustainability – Maintaining quality of soil, air and water
			Preventive and Curative Healthcare
			Disaster Management
			PM National Fund
Ensuring Environmental Sustainability			
Eradicating Poverty			

			Training to promote sports
			Rural Development Projects
3	ICICI Bank Ltd.	Ongoing Projects	---
		Other than Ongoing Projects	Contribution to Prime Minister's Citizen Assistance and Relief in Emergency Situations Fund
			Disaster management
			Preventive healthcare, Hygiene
			Promoting education, employment, enhancing vocational skills
			Livelihood enhancement projects
			ensuring environmental sustainability, ecological balance, protection of flora and fauna, animal welfare, agro forestry, disaster relief, maintaining quality of soil, air and water, making available safe drinking water
			Protection of national heritage, art and culture
			Empowering women, Reducing inequalities
			Rural development
			Making available safe drinking water
4	Indusind Bank Ltd.	Ongoing Projects	Ensuring environmental sustainability
			Promoting Health care
			Enhancing Vocational skills Livelihood enhancement projects
			Promote rural sports, nationally recognised sports, paralympic sports and olympic sports
			Promoting Education
			Disaster & Relief
			Donation
		Other than Ongoing Projects	---
5	Kotak Mahindra Bank Ltd.	Ongoing Projects	Education & Livelihood
			Healthcare
			Sports
			Environment & Sustainable Development
			Relief & Rehabilitation
		Other than Ongoing Projects	Education & Livelihood
			Healthcare
			Sports
			Environment & Sustainable Development
	Relief & Rehabilitation		

The above table shows the ongoing projects as well as other than ongoing projects undertaken in CSR activities of five private sector banks.

7. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

Based on the above data, the findings of the present study are highlighted herein below:

- 1) With effect from 2014, it is mandatory for the corporate to follow the regulatory framework for corporate social responsibility.
- 2) Government guidelines on practices of corporate social responsibility broadly cover all categories such as education, rural development, environment, healthcare, sustainable development, women empowerment, sports, infrastructure, etc.
- 3) Banks are actively involved in CSR activities. Many banks are spending beyond the prescribed limit of two percent of net profit in CSR activities.
- 4) All the private sector banks have allocated 2 percent of their net profit for the purpose of CSR activities. AXIS Bank Ltd., HDFC Bank Ltd. and ICICI Bank Ltd. have spent more than 2 percent of their net profit. However, Indusind Bank Ltd. and Kotak Mahindra Bank Ltd. have spent less than 2 percent of their net profit in CSR activities and thus transfer the unspent amount to Unspent account as per section 135 (6) of the Companies Act.
- 5) Kotak Mahindra Bank Ltd. hold least number of CSR committee meetings i.e. only one meeting while AXIS Bank Ltd. hold maximum number of CSR committee meetings i.e. 4 meetings among all five private sector banks. HDFC Bank and ICICI Bank hold three CSR committee meetings, while Indusind Bank holds two meetings in a year.
- 6) Nearly all the private sector banks have four members in their CSR committee including independent directors, managing director.

8. CONCLUSION

With the introduction of Corporate Social Responsibility in 2013, now in 8 years there have been significant changes in the Corporate Social Responsibility policy brought by the Ministry of Corporate Affairs. Whether a public company or a private company, even subject to certain conditions every company has to be engaged in Corporate Social Responsibility compulsory.. The central government authorities are day by day becoming stricter with the implementation of Corporate Social Responsibility in the corporate world. Not only the government authorities but also the corporate themselves are working with due diligence for Corporate Social Responsibility.

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